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FERTILISATION STRATEGIES ACROSS EUROPE: CURRENT SITUATION, POTENTIAL AND LIMITS FOR A HARMONISED APPROACH

by

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SUMMARY.

A stocktake study, in the framework of the EJP Soil programme¹ took place across 23 European countries to formulate recommendations for harmonising methodologies for delivering fertilisation guidelines. The stocktake revealed substantial differences in the content, format and delivery of current fertilisation guidelines across Europe. Substantial differences exist in soil test methods and how crop nutrient requirements are calculated; even between neighbouring countries, with similar soil types, cropping systems and within the same environmental zone.

The general consensus among all participating countries was that harmonisation of fertilisation guidelines should be increased, in terms of shared learning in the delivery and format of fertilisation guidelines and mechanisms to adhere to environmental legislation. However, it was recognised that it would be difficult, if not impossible, to harmonise soil test data and agronomic requirements at EU-level due to differences in soil types and agro-ecosystems.

Nevertheless, increased future collaboration between neighbouring countries within the same environmental zone was seen as potentially very beneficial, and would contribute to the European Green Deal vision. Particularly, advancement of precision agriculture technology, enabling greatly increased nutrient use efficiency at farm and field level through more site-specific and precise fertiliser placement, and improved rate and timing of nutrient application, could be potentially very beneficial. Shared learning in the use of earth observation technology to generate maps of soil properties, soil nutrients or crop yield variability to make interpretations and contribute to decision making tools would be a potential way of harmonising the methodologies for creating fertilisation recommendations. Country-specific methodology and a lack of harmonisation prohibits the comparison or joint analysis of internationally recognised parameters to evaluate soil nutrient interactions and crop response. While complete harmonisation should not be an end in itself, methods to improve nutrient use efficiency and minimise environmental impact, at field, farm, national and international level, should be the priority.

¹ <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

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Keywords: soil analysis, analytical methodologies, agro-climatic regions, fertiliser recommendations, European comparisons.

1. INTRODUCTION.

1.1. Basis of fertiliser recommendations.

Fertiliser recommendations and advice to farmers are primarily based on agronomic requirements, specific to soil and crop type, and generated individually within each country. The general common principle is to reach or maintain target ranges of plant-available nutrients in soil or to supply plants with adequate nutrient amounts to reach target yields / quantities (Steinfurth *et al.*, 2022). The agricultural sector faces a number of challenges, including producing more food to feed a growing global population, while impacting less on the environment. The basis of good practice should ideally be to make the best economic use of nutrients, while at the same time meeting environmental legislation associated with the EU Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) and the EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), and those underpinning the European Green Deal (COM/2019 640 final) in particular. In many countries, fertiliser recommendations are now capped by nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) application standards (maximum allowable amounts), but nutrient emissions from agriculture need to be reduced further. The key to nutrient management is to apply the optimum amount of nutrient to meet crop requirements, at the right time and in the right place. Measuring, mapping and monitoring of nutrients at field and farm scale are key.

1.2. Differences in fertiliser recommendations between countries.

It has been recognised for many years that considerable differences exist in the content and delivery of fertiliser recommendations across different countries (e.g. Jordan-Meille *et al.*, 2012; ten Berge and van Dijk, 2009), even with similar soil types and within the same environmental zone. Differences in soil nutrient extraction tests exist, within individual countries (Mattila and Rajala, 2022; Steinfurth *et al.*, 2022) and between neighbouring countries (e.g. Vero *et al.*, 2021; Neyroud and Lischer, 2003), along with different methods of calculating fertilisation requirements (e.g. Tóth *et al.*, 2014; Kuchenbuch and Buczko, 2011). EU member states also tend to follow different approaches to tackling nutrient loss and nutrient use efficiency (Klages *et al.*, 2020). Policy measures relating to manure production per hectare, and to the use of stabilised manures and other exogenous organic matter additions can, in many cases, be very successful at reducing emissions (ten Berge and van Dijk, 2009; Vrebos *et al.*, 2017) but further measures are required. Crops are often fertilised above recommended levels to avoid the risk of yield loss, or at a level based on crop yield response and identifying a threshold above which there is no further yield response (Steinfurth *et al.*, 2022). Improving fertilisation techniques, to better match nutrient supply with crop demand and release by the soil would improve overall nutrient use efficiency, particularly N use efficiency (Higgins *et al.*, 2019; Argento *et al.*, 2022). Berry *et al.* (2017) found that the optimum N requirement varied substantially by up to 100 kg N/ha within a 3 ha experimental area. Variation in N optima was found to be negatively related to soil N supply and there was a good relationship between spectral reflectance indices and crop N uptake, which

the authors suggested could potentially have a role in estimating soil N supply

In many cases, differences in soil tests and fertilisation guidelines can operate within close proximity to one another in neighbouring countries or regions, for example in countries separated by a land border (e.g. Vero *et al.*, 2021). This could potentially create confusion or uncertainties among farmers living in border areas. It can also generate issues where there are management requirements and legislation to reduce nutrient losses (N and P) to rivers, lakes or other inland waterbodies within cross-border catchments. Managing nutrient loss from agriculture in these areas can be problematic and requires cooperation and understanding from authorities on both sides of the border. Accounting for trans-boundary air pollution, such as ammonia and nitrous oxide emissions from agriculture and their impact on biodiversity and the amenity value of natural capital, also require consideration.

1.3. Objectives of study.

The objectives of the study were to gather information on how fertilisation guidelines are currently formulated and managed and assess the potential for harmonising the methods between neighbouring countries and across regions in Europe.

This study contributed to the creation of a research roadmap towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils, as part of EJP SOIL, a European Joint Programme project under the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme². There were a number of specific objectives including:

- Objective 1: To complete a stocktake of current fertiliser guidelines across European countries.
- Objective 2: To identify the key variables influencing fertiliser guidelines e.g. climate, soil, cropping system, nutrient loss.
- Objective 3: To identify synergies, similarities and differences in fertilisation guidelines between neighbouring countries.
- Objective 4: To assess the potential for the harmonisation of methodologies and barriers to harmonisation.
- Objective 5: To identify the stakeholders involved in formulating fertilisation guidelines within individual countries.
- Objective 6: To evaluate the importance of knowledge transfer and community engagement.

2. METHODS.

2.1. Completion of stocktake.

A questionnaire was completed by 23 European partners (Table 1), by a person or team within each country who are responsible for or involved in

² <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

compiling and disseminating current fertilisation guidelines within their country. The questionnaire was categorised into six main objectives (detailed above), by formulating specific questions in relation to each objective. Participants answered the questionnaire in Microsoft Excel, providing written responses to each question.

Objective 1: Participants were asked to identify the organisations, institutes and stakeholders involved in formulating the guidelines in their country, and how frequently they are updated. Each country was required to stipulate what environmental zone their country was within, using the classification of Metzger *et al.*, 2005 (Figure 1 and Table 1).

Objective 2: Participants were required to provide details of the main crops and soil types within their country, along with soil tests currently used for phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, calcium, nitrogen, along with the measurement of carbon (Tables 3, 4 and 5).

Objective 3: Participants were asked to identify the differences in current fertilisation practices or soil tests used between their country and their neighbouring countries, specifically if separated by a land border, and how these differences might impact on neighbouring farmers (to the best of their knowledge and awareness). Participants were asked whether there were any potential impacts on cross border river catchments due to nutrient loss, or whether there were specific considerations operating in conservation areas.

Objective 4: Participants were asked their opinion about the relevance of a centralised EU approach to fertilisation management. What would be the main barriers to harmonising fertilisation regimes across countries and environmental zones? What differences are there between countries in the extent to which farmers use precision technology to identify soil or crop nutrient requirements, for example ground sensors, remote sensing or satellite imagery? Do opinions on the importance of precision agriculture using soil and crop sensors and site-specific management for future farming vary between countries? Could precision agriculture techniques (shared principles) and computer or smart phone apps, be a way of harmonising nutrient management and fertilisation practices across EU countries?

Objective 5: Participants were asked to identify the stakeholders involved in formulating fertilisation guidelines within individual countries (Table 2).

Objective 6: Participants were asked to describe, in their personal and professional opinion, the importance of knowledge transfer and community engagement within their country. For example, they had to indicate how fertilisation guidelines are delivered to communities, and the effectiveness of different forms of communication and knowledge transfer.

Table 1: List of participating countries and environmental zone. Each environmental zone is distinguished by a colour in Table 1 and Figure 1.

	Alpine North	Boreal	Nemoral	Atlantic North	Alpine South	Continental	Atlantic Central	Pannonian	Lusitanian	Mediterranean Mountains	Mediterranean North	Mediterranean South
Finland		Grey										
Norway	Purple	Grey		Blue		Light Green						
Latvia			Light Blue									
Lithuania			Light Blue									
Estonia		Grey	Light Blue									
Sweden		Grey	Light Blue			Light Green						
United Kingdom				Blue			Light Blue					
Ireland				Blue			Light Blue					
Germany				Blue	Pink	Light Green	Light Blue	Dark Green				
Denmark				Blue		Light Green						
Netherlands				Blue			Light Blue					
Belgium							Light Blue					
Switzerland					Pink	Light Green				Brown		
Slovakia					Pink	Light Green						
Slovenia					Pink	Light Green		Dark Green				
Austria					Pink	Light Green		Dark Green				
Hungary								Dark Green				
Poland						Light Green						
France					Pink	Light Green	Light Blue		Grey	Brown	Orange	Yellow
Portugal									Grey		Orange	Yellow
Turkey										Brown	Orange	Yellow
Spain					Pink		Light Blue		Grey	Brown	Orange	Yellow
Italy					Pink					Brown	Orange	Yellow

Figure 1: *Environmental zones (ENZ) of Europe according to Metzger et al., (2005), with countries participating in the questionnaire indicated by dashed lines. In this synthesis the following ENZ are represented: Alpine North (ALN); Boreal (BOR); Nemoral (NEM); Atlantic North (ATN); Alpine South (ALS); Continental (CON); Atlantic Central (ATC); Pannonian (PAN); Lusitanian (LUS); Anatolian (ANA); Mediterranean Mountains (MDM); Mediterranean North (MDN); Mediterranean South (MDS).*

3. RESULTS.

3.1. Questionnaire responses.

The results presented below reflect the questionnaire responses, interpreted to the best of the authors' abilities, and as such are dependent, in part, on the knowledge and experience of the individual who completed the questionnaire:

Table 2: Description of the main organisations involved in formulating fertiliser guidelines per participating country (in alphabetical order).

Country	Main organisations responsible for formulating fertilisation guidelines
Austria	The advisory board for soil fertility and soil protection from the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism.
Belgium (Flanders)	Flemish Government, Flemish Government Department of Agriculture and Fisheries, Flemish Government Department of Environment, Flemish Land Agency (VLM), Flemish Environment Agency (VMM), Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Coordination Centre for Information and Guidance on Sustainable Fertilization (CVBB), BoerenBond (BB), Soil Service of Belgium (BDB) and Research and Advisory Board on Sustainable Fertilisation.
Denmark	Aarhus University, SEGES (National Agricultural Advisory Service), LBST (The Danish Agricultural Agency), Copenhagen University and the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark.
Estonia	State agency Agricultural Research Centre, along with other relevant stakeholders.
Finland	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Luke, Farmer's union, fertiliser companies (Yara) and regional authorities.
France	COMIFER (French Committee for the Study and Development of Sustainable Fertilization) is a non-profit-making association which is comparable to a scientific and technical committee. It consists of a platform for exchange and consultation between all the actors interested in fertilisation (research, development, economic actors, public authorities, education). COMIFER is not officially in charge of defining standards, but is in fact the national reference. There is a method of regulation only for nitrogen which results from INRA's research formalised by COMIFER. COMIFER offers reasoning tools, which are generally included in professional tools (field management software, etc.) and educational materials.
Germany	Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture, Federal Ministry for Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection, Julius-Kühn Institute, Thünen Institute, Ministries at federal state level, regional extension services.
Hungary	Ministry of Agriculture, The Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture, Centre for Agricultural Research.
Ireland	Teagasc, Crops, Environment and Land Use Department, Johnstown Castle are responsible for managing and coordinating the updates to the fertilisation guidelines (Government-funded research organisation).
Italy	A specific group of experts ("Agronomic Techniques Group", GTA) established by the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies.
Latvia	Cabinet of Ministries manage official regulations. Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Latvia in collaboration with Latvian University of Agriculture develop manuals with recommendations and learning materials.
Lithuania	Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC) in cooperation with Lithuanian Advisory Service in the order of Ministry of Agriculture. The newest recommendation provided in the Code for Good Agricultural Practices.

Country	Main organisations responsible for formulating fertilisation guidelines
Netherlands	There are standing committees which develop the fertilisation guidelines specific for grassland and fodder crops and specific for arable crops and vegetables. These committees consist of researchers, independent advisors, representatives of soil laboratories and farmers organisations.
Norway	Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU), Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO) and Norwegian Agricultural Extension Service (NLR).
Poland	Polish Fertilizer Society CIEC.
Portugal	National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinarian Research I.P. (INIAV).
Slovakia	Central Control and Testing Institute in Agriculture, Bratislava.
Slovenia	Ministry of Agriculture in cooperation with UL-BF, AIS and UM-FKBV
Spain	Ministry of Agriculture and regional governments. Implementation and support to end-users is carried out at the local regional level.
Sweden	Swedish Board of Agriculture.
Switzerland	Agroscope – the Swiss centre of excellence for agricultural research, affiliated to the Federal Office for Agriculture (FOAG) within the Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research (EAER).
Turkey	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry.
United Kingdom	There is a nutrient management committee in the UK, made up of representatives from England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. AHDB (An agricultural levy board in the UK) are in overall charge of compiling the recommendations, along with input from research organisations, farm advisory groups, Department of Agriculture representatives from England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland, and there are also national farmers union representatives.

3.2. A stocktake of current fertilisation guidelines.

The 23 countries surveyed each operate independently in terms of development and management of fertilisation guidelines specific to their country (Austria, Belgium (Flanders), Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom). Fertilisation guidelines are updated, on average every ten years, but the frequency of updates was highly variable between countries. Thirty seven percent of respondents reported that small amendments are made regularly (on-demand, annually or every 2-4 years) in accordance with the latest research findings and, particularly in relation to environmental legislation (France, Netherlands, UK, Ireland and Finland). For a small number of countries (18% of countries who responded e.g. Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuanian), fertilisation guidelines are less frequently updated (> 10 years between updates). Three countries make annual revisions to their guidelines (UK, Italy, Sweden), but mainly just small changes for individual crops, such as cereals or oil seed rape.

While fertilisation guidelines in some countries are developed solely by universities, research institutes or through government advisory services, in the majority of countries (83%) there is a designated committee responsible for the formulation of fertilisation guidelines (Table 2). This comprises representatives from research, economic actors, government bodies, public authorities, education and farmers organisations; and involves collective decision making. In some countries soil laboratories and commercial fertiliser companies are also involved.

3.3. Key variables directing fertilisation guidelines.

Fertilisation recommendations for the main plant nutrients (N, P, K) are primarily based on the agronomic requirements for specific crops. All participating countries stated that nutrient loss and environmental protection are important considerations in the fertiliser guidelines for their country, and adjustments have been made to fertilisation recommendations and best management practices in order to minimise nutrient loss to the environment and meet legislative requirements. Other important factors taken into consideration, and which varied by individual countries, and regionally within countries, included recent fertilisation history, preceding crop, and organic manure management (organic fertiliser type, manure or slurry source) and soil parameters such as texture, organic matter content, pH and carbonate content. In total, more than 10 soil phosphorus tests were identified as being used within the 23 participating countries (Table 3). In some countries more than one soil test for phosphorus is used within a single country (for example in the Netherlands, Switzerland, France, Portugal, Turkey and Italy). The most frequently used soil P tests across participating countries were the Olsen soil P test (sodium bicarbonate), and the Egner-Riehm method (ammonium lactate) (Table 3). Other less frequently used tests include Joret-Hébert (ammonium oxalate) and Dyer tests (citric acid), mainly used in France and a CO₂-saturated water method used in Switzerland (Hirte *et al.*, 2021; Jordon-Meille *et al.*, 2012).

In addition to the variation in soil phosphorus tests used, soil analysis methods for carbon, potassium, magnesium, calcium and nitrogen also vary widely between countries (Tables 3, 4, 5 and 6). Although not directly required for fertiliser recommendations, dry combustion was the most frequently recorded method (52% of responses) of measuring total soil carbon, followed by wet oxidation method (26% of responses) (Table 4).

The most frequently applied method for measuring plant available K, Mg, Ca was by ammonium acetate extraction (Table 5), the second one being ammonium lactate extraction (Egner-Riehm method). Even within these common tests, there were variations in method descriptions between countries and terminology used. Soil nitrogen content (total or mineral N) is not routinely measured in many countries (e.g. Norway, Estonia, UK, Ireland), but where required; total N is most commonly measured via dry combustion or by Kjeldahl analysis (wet acid digestion), and mineral N by KCl extraction

Table 3: *List of plant available soil phosphorus chemical extractant methods recorded by participating countries.*

	Austria	BE (Flanders)	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Netherlands	Norway	Poland	Portugal	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Turkey	UK
0.5 M sodium bicarbonate pH 8.5 (Olsen et al., 1954)			X		X	X				X						X			X			X	X
0.1 M ammonium lactate 0.4 N acetic acid, pH 3.75 (Egner et al., 1960)		X						X			X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X			
Remoisture of soil 1-2 mL soil + 2 mL water (Sissingh, 1971)													X										
0.05 M calcium acetate + calcium lactate +0.05 M + 0.3 M acetic acid pH 4.1 (Schüller, 1969)	X						X						X										
0.015 M ammonium fluoride + 0.2 M acetic acid + 0.025 M ammonium nitrate + 0.013 M nitric acid, pH 2.5 (Mehlich, 1984)				X						X							X						
Sodium acetate acetic acid, pH 4.8 (Morgan's 1941) *									X														
0.03 M ammonium fluoride + 0.025 M hydrochloric acid (Bray and Kurtz, 1945)										X													X
1:5 citric acid 2% (Dyer, 1894)						X																X	
0.2 M ammonium oxalate (Joret and Hebert, 1955)						X																	
1:2.5, water saturated in CO ₂ (Dirks and Scheffer, 1930)													X									X	
0.5 M ammonium acetate + EDTA 0.02 M pH 4.65 (Van den Hende and Cottenie, 1960)																						X	

* Modified Morgan's method used in parts of Scotland (0.5 M ammonium acetate/acetic acid adjusted to pH 4.5) (MISR/SAC. 1985).

Table 4: *Principles and methods of measuring total soil carbon in soil across participating countries.*

Country	Dry Combustion (ISO 10694)	Wet Oxidation (ISO 14235)	Loss on Ignition
Austria	X		
Belgium (Flanders)	X		
Denmark	X		
Estonia	X	X	
Finland	X		X
France	X	X	
Germany	X		
Hungary		X	
Ireland	X		X
Italy	X	X	
Latvia	X		
Lithuania			
Netherlands			X
Norway			X
Poland			
Portugal	X	X	
Slovakia		X	
Slovenia	X		
Spain	X	X	
Sweden	X		X
Switzerland		X	
Turkey	X		X
United Kingdom	X		X

Table 5: *Methods of measuring plant available K, Mg, Ca in soil across participating countries.*

	Austria	BE (Flanders)	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Netherlands	Norway	Poland	Portugal	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland *	Turkey	UK
Ammonium acetate	X		X		X	X				X	X					X		X	X		X	X	X
Ammonium lactate (Egner-Riehm)		X						X			X	X		X		X		X	X	X			
Sodium acetate						X																	
Hydrochloric acid and oxalic acid)													X										
0.01M CaCl ₂							X						X								X		
Cobalt-hexamine combined with NIRS													X										
Mehlich-3				X						X							X						
Morgan's									X														
Calcium acetate lactate (Schüller)	X																						

* K: CO₂-saturated water; 1:10 water, Ammonium acetate – EDTA.

Mg: CaCl₂; 1:10 water; Ammonium acetate – EDTA.

Ca: Ammonium acetate – EDTA.

Table 6: *Methods of measuring soil nitrogen in participating countries.*

	Austria	BE (Flanders)	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Netherlands	Norway	Poland	Portugal	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Turkey	UK
Total N by Dry combustion (NF ISO 13878)			X			X			X	X	X		X						X				X
Total N by Kjeldahl (NF ISO 112261)						X				X	X	X				X	X		X			X	X
Potentially mineralisable N by ÖNORM L 1204	X																						
Mineral N (N _{min}) by 1M or 2M KCl extraction		X	X					X	X	X		X				X			X			X	X
Mineral N (N _{min}) by CaCl ₂ extraction							X											X			X		
Not measured in routine analysis				X					X				X	X						X			X
No information provided					X																		

(Table 6). Classifying plant available soil N for crop N fertiliser recommendations is generally on chemical basis – total N, mineral N (NH₄, NO₃ etc) and organic N, and this level of detail and methodology also varied widely between countries. In the UK, for example, crop N recommendations are based on a combination of factors including classification of soil nitrogen supply (determined by soil type, previous crop, management or rainfall, for example), combined with target yields and source of N (organic manures or mineral fertiliser). In Sweden, the stocktake reported that efforts are being made to estimate actual plant available N. In the early cropping season, before flowering, the crop N content in zero N plots is often estimated through handheld optical sensors or by visual inspection. For the distribution of open general advice such estimates are made on numerous fields by the Swedish Board of Agriculture and on another set of fields by Yara. In Sweden the Yara N Sensor is widely used to estimate crop N content.

3.4. Identification of synergies, similarities and differences between systems.

In general, common across all countries is the completion of soil analysis, the identification of the nutritional needs of crops, the interpretation of soil test results and formulation of a fertilisation plan in relation to the pedo-climatic conditions. The methods of communication of fertilisation guidelines varies greatly between countries, some countries providing great detail in how to build the fertilisation plan (e.g. France, Switzerland and Austria). According to answers provided in the questionnaire, other countries, such as Slovenia, use a similar conceptual approach, but the communication is simplified. Most European countries allocate soil analyses results to four to six classes, ranging from low to high nutrient content but the detail and interpretation of results and how it is presented to farmers varies greatly. Many countries, such as the UK and Ireland, are aware of the methods used to formulate fertilisation guidelines in their neighbouring countries, and the format in which they are published. Other countries in this study reported that they are aware that differences exist but are not familiar with the detail, and there is a lack of shared information available (for example Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia and Turkey). However, it is unclear whether this information is unavailable or simply unknown to the person completing the questionnaire.

Differences in farm type and management intensity vary between neighbouring countries. As an example; there are differences in the prevalence of forest in Sweden compared to intensively managed agricultural land in Denmark. Compared to Sweden, the farm animal density and availability of manure is much higher in Denmark. Spain and Portugal reported being similar in their fertilisation guidelines, while differences with France are more apparent, mainly driven by differences in the type of agro-ecosystems between the countries. For farmers living in border regions between countries, it was recognised that there are likely to be differences in fertilisation regimes operating within close proximity. However, this has been under-reported and while many countries expect that differences exist along border regions, they have not been quantified and the implications have not been reported and discussed among neighbouring countries. Belgium (Flanders) reported that

there may be farmers who own land parcels across border areas, and they must comply with different fertilisation guidelines for different land parcels. In Ireland there are different soil tests used between Ireland and Northern Ireland (UK) but the guidelines in general are similar between these countries, with shared environmental concerns and agronomic crop requirements. A final example is in Portugal, where near the border in the south of the country there are intensive olive groves that are managed by Spanish technicians, using the fertilisation guidelines developed in Spain.

3.5. Potential and barriers for harmonisation of methodologies.

Overall, there was unanimous (100%) support amongst countries for some kind of harmonisation, or standardisation, of fertilisation guidelines between neighbouring countries. However, it was emphasised that this should only be where soil type, growing conditions, crop rotations and yields are comparable. Climatic variation across Europe has a huge influence on nutrient cycling and nutrient availability, which in turn influences fertilisation recommendations (for example between northern and southern European countries) (Quernada and Gabriel, 2016; Gabriel and Quernada, 2017). Harmonisation of fertilisation guidelines is relevant for competitiveness, for example in terms of surplus manure which must be stored and treated. For environmental and climatic aspects it is important to use the same indicators for impact of fertilisation, such as legacy soil P or N surplus. Cooperation between countries can lead to improved fertilisation guidelines. However, harmonisation should not be a goal in itself. It was recognised that harmonisation and alignment of fertilisation guidelines between neighbouring countries and regions would be difficult, if not impossible, and should be evaluated case by case. Rather than aiming to harmonise advice, sharing of knowledge was rated as being very valuable and should be strengthened. Full harmonisation may not be necessary.

3.6. Precision agriculture.

To some level, precision agriculture (PA) is implemented by farmers within all countries surveyed, but generally the percentage of farmers implementing precision technology is relatively low in many regions and the % uptake varies depending on the technology. However, uptake is increasing, especially for variable rate fertilisation and several decision support systems are now available and in use. France and Germany reported some of the highest adoption rates amongst countries surveyed (Paustian and Theuvsen, 2017). In the Netherlands it is estimated that approximately 15% of the farmers use satellite imagery, soil scans and variable rate fertiliser application, and for Switzerland, 17% of the farmers are estimated to have adopted such technologies (Groher et al., 2020). France has been using satellite imagery for guiding N fertilisation in cereals for a number of years. In Sweden and Denmark the free of charge platform CropSAT³ is being widely used. An increase in PA adoption may be expected when the techniques become

³ cropsat.dk and cropsat.se

cheaper, the accuracy improves, the technique becomes easier-to-use and when legislation becomes more customised and extended to more crops and geographical areas. There is currently much active ongoing research in this area. In Estonia, the questionnaire results reported less than 5%, and in Italy and Hungary only 1-2% of the farmers use precision agriculture techniques. However, automated steering on farm vehicles may be used by more than 50% of farmers in Estonia. The value and potential benefit of adopting such techniques is strongly recognised and their application is growing over time. In Scandinavia, Germany, UK and Baltic countries N sensors for nitrogen are frequently used in grain farming. In Sweden the total acreage of winter wheat fertilised with a variable rate of N is estimated to be approximately 50%. Many of the countries surveyed consider that precision agriculture using soil and crop sensors and site specific land management is important in future farming. However, much research and development are still required in integrating these methods on farms. The use of smart phone apps, nutrient management planning computer programmes, and precision agriculture principles could possibly be used as the basis for harmonising management practices across EU countries and more specifically within discrete environmental zones. In addition, aside from using technology, precision fertilisation also implies an increase in data accuracy with respect to fertilisation. For example, data on nutrient concentration of organic fertilisers, use of crop removal coefficients and monitoring of plant requirements.

4. DISCUSSION.

Here we discuss the perceived potential benefits, along with barriers, of a more harmonised approach to fertilisation strategies across Europe, based on the stocktake study described. By harmonisation, we refer to the methods used to formulate fertilisation recommendations, such as the way we sample soils; the laboratory extraction methods used; laboratory quantification methods used on extracts; the factors accounted for such as previous crop and management history; and how we interpret soil test values. For fertilisation recommendations, differences in laboratory extraction methods for plant available nutrients are most important, whereas differences in methods for measuring total nutrients is less important for fertilisation, but more important, for example, for C accounting or describing a soils overall 'health' or 'function'. Perhaps harmonisation should start by defining a standardised approach by which we gather and analyse soil and crop data and how this data is then used to formulate fertilisation guidelines. Individual countries generally operate their own standard protocols, but currently there is no standardised European approach. We conclude with methodologies and recommendations for future research and progress in this area.

The first thing we need to ask is: why would we consider a more harmonised approach to fertilisation across Europe? What need is there for increased harmonisation, and what benefit would it bring over the current situation? It became clear during the stocktake that there are many different aspects to

these questions. There are obvious differences such as soil type, crop and climatic factors, which determine fertilisation strategies, and would be difficult to change, and there are good reasons not to change them. However, the growing importance of the environment and climate change and the need to create a roadmap towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils, gives us greater incentive and reason to question current practice. The European Green Deal⁴ aims to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy with no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, along with a Soils Strategy⁵ to restore soils and make them more resilient, make food more healthy and affordable, and to foster fresh air, clean water, healthy soil and biodiversity. To achieve this objective it is essential that we become more efficient, resourceful and aware of how we are managing our landscape. Much can be learned from questioning current practice and looking for alternatives, solutions and learning from others. This is particularly relevant for climate change scenarios, for example where learning can be gained by cooler northern countries from experience acquired in warmer, more southern countries. The EU FaST tool⁶ is a digital service supported by DG Agriculture and Rural Development, the EU Space Programme and the EU ISA Programme. The vision of the FaST tool is to provide solutions for sustainable and competitive agriculture based on data spatialisation (Copernicus and Galileo) and other public and private databases. Fertilisation recommendations are within the FaST applications, based on overlaying farm data with Copernicus/Sentinel imagery. However, spatial imagery information is not always relevant to inform soil nutrient availability (particularly soil P). The FaST tool is proposed under Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) as part of the new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) proposal. A farm-gate balance module could be integrated into FaST as a quick and easy digital tool that could be used by all countries.

Perhaps one of the main barriers to harmonisation of fertilisation strategies and guidelines, and most historically recognised factors, are the huge differences in soil types and soil nutrient testing methods between European countries, as shown by the present study. Jordan-Meille *et al.*, (2012) presented apparent contradictions in the interpretation of soil-P test values and more than 3-fold differences in the P fertiliser recommendations for similar soil-crop situations. Jordan-Meille *et al.*, (2012) called for a mechanistic approach and a single standard method or simulated sorption-desorption models. To date there is no unified legislation at the European level defining the maximum P amount applicable to agricultural soils due to the different fate of P applied to acidic or calcareous soils, and the differences in the analytical methods as well as the strength of the extractants. In all countries there are restrictions in fertilisation within conservation areas and nature reserves, and there are regulations for organic materials, particularly sewage sludge.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu>; COM(2019) 640 final

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/publications/eu-soil-strategy-2030_en

⁶ <https://fastplatform.eu/>

Having standard tests across Europe would facilitate the exchange of scientific data, creating real and meaningful comparisons (Tunney *et al.*, 1997). However, the principal of soil testing involves the characterisation of plant available nutrients by chemical extraction, but even at a country- or regional-level, there are complex discrepancies and variability when quantifying nutrient pools using different extracting solutions: consequently, standardising nutrient extraction methods all over European countries appears difficult since national methods are sometimes highly consolidated and responsive to specific soil pedological characteristics. Continuing with P as an example, Nawara *et al.* (2017) stated that most soil tests for available P perform rather poorly in predicting crop response, but no soil test was clearly superior to the others. Bell *et al.* (2005, 2005a) presented evidence of where within-country soil type differences can result in variances in the effectiveness of a particular soil test designated as the country-specific test. Including soil parameters such as texture and soil organic matter in addition to plant-available P content was suggested by Buczko *et al.*, (2018) as helpful to improve P fertilisation recommendations. Differences in cross-border soil test methods can present challenges for managing shared waterbodies. This becomes problematic where there are contrasting fertiliser recommendations between neighbouring farms in cross-border regions and where there are water quality issues relating to agricultural nutrient loss (Vero *et al.*, 2021). Many complex interacting factors should be considered, which is why authors have recognised discrepancies in soil test methods and procedures for many years, and often poor correlation among those tests, but alternatives or resolutions have not been forthcoming. Alternatives are leaf analysis and grain analysis. These methods could be introduced EU-wide, parallel to local soil analytical methods: the plant acting as a monitor of nutrient supply.

Tighter legislation on fertiliser use, particularly manure application in intensive animal production areas, is viewed as being crucial to achieve further reductions in surplus nutrient input and emissions across Europe (ten Berge and van Dijk, 2009). A better foundation for fertiliser recommendations is necessary. It is widely recognised that N fertiliser recommendations for several crops vary widely between member states. In a workshop held in the Netherlands in 2009, discussing ways in which nutrient losses from agriculture could be reduced, ten Berge and van Dijk (2009) summarised that, given the important role of N recommendations, an international comparative audit of the science behind recommendations would be highly relevant. There is little common EU-wide knowledge on nitrogen budgeting and its comparability at the farm level for the detection of ground and surface water pollution caused by nitrates and the monitoring of mitigation measures (Klages *et al.*, 2020). There is some flexibility within the Nitrates Directive for Member States, which is positive, but Klages *et al.*, (2020) recognised that a more integrated approach to nutrient management is required. For example, this could involve stronger exchange on scientific knowledge, with perhaps a more unified system of registration, monitoring and inspection for wider areas in Europe. However, a consensus on agricultural soil management practices would need to be in place first. The development of more

harmonised fertilisation guidelines, which at least overcome discrepancies linked to overly empirical evaluations and implement an agreed selection of scientifically based methods, would be extremely important to allow truly balanced mineral and organic fertiliser inputs. The focus here is not confined to N and P. This stocktake study also revealed differences in methodologies for measuring and interpreting soil carbon. Carbon and carbon measurements are included within fertiliser recommendations in some, but not all regions. Carbon plays a crucial role in understanding and monitoring soil health, organic matter and soil nutrient dynamics, particularly N balance and availability for follow-on crops. This will be very important going forward as we work towards Net Zero targets, and the importance of soil as a sink for carbon (Poepflau *et al.*, 2022; Smith *et al.*, 2020). In terms of national carbon accounting it would be very important that carbon accounting methods are standardised and follow the same protocols (FAO, 2020). Until recently, for national inventories, carbon budgets are (almost always) modelled, not measured. The applied methods (tier 1, 2 and 3 methods) strongly depend on the country's means. In addition, the overall management of fertilisation to achieve either an economical or environmental optimum is not yet defined or harmonised between countries.

However, change in current practice (soil tests and fertilisation recommendations) would need to be considered over time. An evolution that is too rapid would lead to a distortion of competition between countries, depending on their initial situation and the new standards they would have to share, in terms of application rates and methods. The assimilation of new methods by farmers is a crucial issue, when in many cases even the current national methods are variably implemented within their own countries. Some countries within the stocktake felt that for detailed guidelines and regulations there should not be a centralised EU approach because conditions are too different. Best management practices for both production and environment are those adapted to local conditions. Analytical methods, purpose and possible gains must be carefully evaluated, and an EU-wide evaluation of trial results would need to be coordinated. The local adaptation needed at the farm and field scale for efficient use of resources should be considered. There are indications that the optimal N rate in some countries may be substantially higher for the same crop and the same harvest than in other countries. To establish such circumstances and to investigate plausible reasons and environmental and economic consequences may be of considerable interest. Ideally there would need to be fertiliser response trials for contrasting crops, environments and soil types. Some published trial data exists (for example Tajnšek *et al.*, 2013; Spiegel *et al.*, 2010; Csitári *et al.*, 2021) however, an overall evaluation is missing. Crops and their growing period differ widely from south to north. Inter-country benchmarking, development and use of a more harmonised method of assessing soil N supply (N in soil at sowing plus N mineralisation rate) and integrating differentiated recommendations for yield level would be an important target and thus should be strengthened.

Precision farming techniques are continuously developing and offer rapid diagnosis of crop N status e.g. reflection measurement by crop sensing and/ or soil N status, variable rate fertiliser applications (e.g. Spiegel *et al.*, 2020; Higgins *et al.*, 2019; Argento *et al.*, 2020). Further promising technologies include targeted placement of fertilisers near plant roots along with better timing and dosage based on crop / soil indicators. Precision agriculture developments, by increasing efficiency within agricultural systems, will directly impact fertiliser recommendation systems going forward. Instead of blanket country-specific recommendations, future fertiliser recommendations could take into consideration farm-specific decision support systems, integrating site, soil, plant and climatic data during the growing season. Cowan *et al.*, (2021) estimated that up to 20% savings could be made by not applying N where it is unnecessary to do so. The new Farm to Fork Strategy and its aim to reduce N fertilisation by 20% will further contribute to more targeted N fertilisation. Recommendations also need to be updated regularly due to improved cultivars and crop varieties that differ in their nutrient uptake and demand. In future, the continued development of artificial intelligence and high performance computing could have more of a role in the monitoring of soil and crops, with upscaling of field data to catchment and national scale. Proximal sensors provide measurements of ground data, which is particularly useful for generating data on soil properties. The fusion of data from proximal and remote sensing systems, along with real-time samples or long-term benchmark monitoring sites can be very powerful (Smith *et al.*, 2020). Predicting nutrient levels has been suggested as being feasible with sensor fusion and information from several soil and crop sensors at once. Multi-sensor platforms for sensing soil are likely to play a bigger role in future (Escolà and Kerry 2021). In order for farmers to take advantage of these digital opportunities, training courses and access to user friendly tools and smart phone apps are indispensable. The technical and economic benefits still need to be quantified. For the best global agricultural and environmental outcomes, we need to question whether the priority is more technology for a small number of advanced farmers or an effective implementation of simple, moderately performing methods by a greater number. Precision agriculture may, together with accurately measuring plant available nutrients by traditional extraction methods, in combination with new analytical approaches such as leaf and grain analytics, enable a step forward towards a more nutrient-efficient, environmentally-friendly and economic plant production.

5. CONCLUSIONS.

The overall objective of this study was to assess the potential for harmonising methods used for formulating fertilisation guidelines between neighbouring countries and across regions in Europe. Accountability of nutrient use at field, farm and national level is increasing in importance. There would be many benefits of a more harmonised approach to fertilisation recommendations across Europe, although it is unclear as to what form that would be in. Full harmonisation is unlikely to be possible, or desirable. However, by sharing

principles of soil monitoring, analytical methods and technological advances there may be beneficial outcomes for both production and the environment.

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